

INCREASING TOURIST LOYALTY TO VISIT LAKE TOBA BY MAXIMIZING TOUR FACILITIES, NOSTALGIA, AND ATTRACTION THROUGH BRAND IMAGE

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Abstract

This study's primary goal is to ascertain the direct and indirect effects of tourist attractions, nostalgia, and facilities on visitor loyalty as measured by brand perception. Data for the current study were gathered by distributing questionnaires, making it quantitative research. The study's participants are visitors who have been to Lake Toba. Three hundred twenty tourists were chosen to represent the research sample in the incidental sampling method used to collect the sample. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on AMOS was used to examine the data. The findings demonstrated that all factors—tour facilities, nostalgia, and attraction—directly and significantly impacted the brand's perception and customer loyalty among visitors to Lake Toba. Brand reputation, however, has little impact on repeat business from tourists. Additionally, the perception of a brand indirectly plays a crucial role in moderating the effects of tour amenities, nostalgia, and attractiveness on the adherence of visitors to Lake Toba.

Keywords: tour facilities, nostalgia, attraction, brand image, loyalty

1. INTRODUCTION

The growth of the tourism industry in modern times has attracted a great deal of attention, particularly from various stakeholders. It is anticipated that the tourism industry's contribution would be able to continue to enhance the town's economic situation (Ashley et al., 2007; Mendoza-Ramos & Prideaux, 2018). Therefore, there is a need for solid administration in the tourist industry to increase visitor interest (Jenkins & Henry, 1982; Dinica, 2009). It is anticipated that the singularity that characterizes particular locations will be a significant asset, increasing the number of visitors (Crouch & Ritchie, 1999; Smith, 2012). As a result, it will constitute a distinguishing characteristic that any area can provide to pique the interest of tourists (Chang, 2006; Franch et al., 2008).

The National Tourism Strategic Area (NTSA) of Lake Toba has excellent potential to become a developing tourist destination, so Lake Toba is appropriate and very feasible to be developed into a National Tourism Destination (Hajar et al., 2021; Purwoko et al., 2021). The natural resources, cultural practices, and artistic production found there are all different and original, which is why it attracts so many tourists. "To make Lake Toba a national standard tourist destination, this largest volcanic lake in the world needs to be addressed immediately, and the marketing system must be organized better," said Head of Public Relations of the Samosir Regency Government, Gomgom Naibaho in Pangururan. Even the tourist attraction of this most beautiful tropical lake on the equator, measuring 87-kilometer long and 27-kilometer

wide, includes various interesting elements with a unique historical background. Consequently, it merits being promoted as a site for tourists from all over the world, to the extent that the growth of a country's tourism industry is a top priority (Paramitha et al., 2019; Rini & Absah, 2020).

North Sumatra is one of Indonesia's provinces with many potential world-class tourist attractions. The high contribution of the tourism sector can be seen by the indicator that there is an increase in visits to tourist destinations (Situmorang et al., 2019; Marpaung et al., 2016). The following is data on tourist visits to North Sumatra Province:

Table 1: Total Tourist Visits to North Sumatra Province

No.	Year	Foreign Tourist	Domestic Tourist	Total
1	2015	375,166	31,432,080	31,807,246
2	2016	375,166	36,899,776	37,478,700
3	2017	781,107	40,228,470	40,899,577
4	2018	781,107	48,943,607	49,620,775
5	2019	691,699	57,900,863	58,592,562
	Total	3,104,064	215,294,796	218,398,860

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics of North Sumatra Province, 2019

According to the table above, the number of tourist visits to North Sumatra Province increased significantly between 2015 and 2019. The community surrounding the tourist attraction area has a significant potential to boost their income through business operations conducted or opened in the attraction region, such as cafes, restaurants, and kiosks selling food and beverages (Wilson et al., 2001; Nyaupane et al., 2006). The fall in international tourism to North Sumatra is a problem that must be addressed. North Sumatra must continue to attract as many tourists as Java, Bali, and West Sumatra. In addition, North Sumatra is still hampered by a lack of suitable infrastructure for tourism objects, a dearth of investors in the construction of public facilities and infrastructure, and difficulty with the quality of tourism products to be promoted and sold. North Sumatra still relies on the arrival of foreign tourists from Malaysia, Singapore, China, and Germany to boost the economy from the tourism sector, even though North Sumatra has the potential to attract tourists with tours of lakes, seas, mountains, forests, cities, heritage, culinary, and food souvenirs (Causey, 2003; Bruner, 2005).

Barnes (2013) states that establishing loyalty begins with value creation, satisfaction, retention, and loyalty. This implies that enhancing customer value can boost customer satisfaction and lead to more excellent customer retention (Reichheld, 1994). When customers stay because they are comfortable with the value and service they get, they are more likely to become loyal customers (Mascarenhas et al., 2006). (Mascarenhas et al., 2006). According to Wibowo and Yuniawati's (2010) findings, visitor loyalty does not occur automatically but after the satisfaction stage. While Gunarto's (2009) research suggested that corporate image is an intervening variable for the effect of the promotional mix variable on customer loyalty, consumer happiness is also an intervening variable. This is consistent with Lache and Alexa's

(2011) assertion that the quality of services, enticing promotions, and attractions provided to tourists will affect their loyalty. Ronsumbre (2012) links tourism items, service quality, marketing mix, and environmental circumstances to tourist satisfaction and tourist loyalty in the tourist area of the city of Biak Numfor based on the phenomena that exist in this tourist region. Service quality is the effort to meet client requirements and wishes and the precision with which services are delivered to match consumer expectations (Zeithaml et al., 1996).

According to Rita Milyartini (2012), in order that we are not constantly in a culture that is tossed about due to the globalization process, a strategy is needed to develop cultural security, namely the ability to preserve and optimize cultural values in the creative process that can improve the nation's quality of life (De Vries & Petersen, 2009). Dodi Taruna (2000) states that to increase tourist visits, it is necessary to develop tourist attractions and various facilities and infrastructure needed by utilizing existing potential. The development of tourist attractions must be oriented to the wishes of tourists by paying attention to the carrying capacity of the community environment (Novelli, 2022). Norrizal (2000) states that the show as an end of the accumulation of the creative process is carried out by several variants, where there is a link between one element and another to complement each other in a unified whole; one cannot be separated from the other, because of the loss of one element of the variant will reduce the final quality of the displayed form. Gusniva Iryani (2000) states that dance is an artistic statement, so dance's nature, style, and function cannot be separated from the culture that produces it.

Cultural heritage has become significant in light of the relentless modernization and globalization of cities worldwide, which, if unchecked, will result in an identical urban appearance in every city (Adhisakti, 2001). This historic structure is an economical, social, and cultural value to the state, and historical structures are a source of revenue to increase foreign exchange through international tourist visits. According to Sankar (2015), the most significant aspect of legacy tourism is the cultural interchange between different nations visiting other countries. His research reveals that historical tourism has the effect of enhancing regional income through tourist visitation. According to Sally's (2015) research findings, legacy tourism as cultural capital can promote tourist visits and boost economic growth in Mali and Ethiopia.

Tourism is tangible and intangible in a continuum of journeys that can only be enjoyed if the complete trip series offers a positive experience to individuals who take them (Hall & Lew, 2009; Muljadi, 2009). According to Freyer (1993) (quoted in Damanick & Weber, 2006, p. 11), a tourist product is any item designed for or consumed during tourism activities. According to Burkart and Medlik (in Freyer, 1993), tourism services are a composite product comprised of attractions, transportation, lodging, and entertainment.

Andreassen and Lindestad (1998), Kadampully and Suhartanto (2000), Pong et al., (2001), Beerli et al., (2004), Ollorunniwo et al. (2006), Gonzales et al. (2007), Yen & Lu (2008), and Sahadev and Purani (2009) have conducted research related tourism products, satisfaction, and loyalty (2008). According to the findings of Pong et al. (2001), Beerli et al. (2004), and Ollorunniwo et al. (2006), service tourism items have a considerable impact on customer satisfaction. Ioannis, Chaniotakis, and Constantine (2009) studied the impact of tourism

products and services (tangibles, responsiveness, empathy, assurance, and dependability) on customer satisfaction. Moreover, Lache and Alexa (2011) studied several facets of consumer loyalty toward tourism products. The results indicated that tourism products, facilities, and culture correlate with consumer satisfaction and that consumer satisfaction influences consumer loyalty. Murphy et al. (2011) indicate that tourism products consisting of specific regional items, shopping areas, and entertainment venues satisfy tourists. As a comparative benchmark for gauging visitor satisfaction, tourist expectations play a crucial role in the context of tourist satisfaction. According to Tjiptono and Chandra (2005), expectations are preexisting individual ideas about what should occur in specific scenarios. Customer expectations are customer beliefs before testing or purchasing a product, which is used as a standard or reference to evaluate the product's performance (Olson and Dover in Zeithaml et al., 2006). However, tourist satisfaction is not enough. Prahalad and Hamel stated that every organization should focus on opportunities to compete in the future (Reichheld, 1996, in Raharso, 2005). The trick is to get loyal customers (Seybold, 2001, Raharso, 2005). Many studies examine and analyze tourist satisfaction as an antecedent that affects tourist loyalty (Som et al., 2011).

Another phenomenon that causes tourist satisfaction and loyalty to decline in traditional values. Traditional values are cultural values that must be adequately managed and preserved to attract more tourists (Besculides & McCormick, 2002; Liu, 2003). The problem so far is that the strengthening of traditional values in Lake Toba has not been maximized. Traditional values as a tourist attraction can support tourist satisfaction and loyalty. According to Law No. 10 of 2009 of the Republic of Indonesia, a tourist attraction is anything that has originality, beauty, and worth in the form of a diversity of natural, cultural, and manufactured richness and is the aim or purpose of tourist visits. Specifically, natural tourism attractions are defined as everything that is the aim or purpose of tourist visits and possess uniqueness, beauty, authenticity, and values in the form of a diversity of natural richness (Kirillova et al., 2014; Tasci, 2011). Damanik and Weber (2006) emphasize the importance of authenticity in determining the quality of a tourist attraction, both in terms of originality and authenticity.

This study differs from past research in that it examines nostalgia as a characteristic of tourism items and traditional attraction value, neither of which has been previously examined (Yoon & Uysal, 2005; Chi & Qu, 2008; Josephus Ronsumbre, 2012; Campo-Martinez et al., 2010; and Kozak, 2001). The difference thus rests in the author's SEM analysis model, which differs from earlier investigations. According to Lamidi & Rahadhini (2011), the increasing number of tourists is related to the added value they receive in the form of cultural knowledge and experience, as well as comfort, which can increase the likelihood that they will visit again. Following their argument, it is necessary to recognize the significance of nostalgia as an attribute of tourism products.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND SUBMISSION OF HYPOTHESES

2.1 Tourist Facilities

Tourism infrastructure is a crucial aspect of tourism development. Tourism facilities can be seen as a business that directly or indirectly provides services to tourists in a tourist destination where its existence is highly dependent on the existence of tourist travel activities. Not infrequently, travelers are drawn to a place, area, or country by the comforts that can be achieved through the available amenities (Situmeang, 2001). Moreover, all tourist facilities are designed to fulfill the demands of visitors who temporarily reside in the tourist sites they visit, where they can enjoy and engage in various activities at their leisure (Dzakiya, 2020).

2.2 Nostalgia/Travel Attributes

The word nostalgia comes from the Greek (Liddell and Scott, 1958, p. 467.31) pronounced "nosto," meaning to return home, and pronounced "Algia," meaning a painful condition. Thus, nostalgia is the longing to return home. Nostalgia, a longing from time to time, can create several sequences of events that lead to nostalgia. The sequence of nostalgic occurrences includes (1) Physiological and Anatomical Theories, (2) Environmental Theories, (3) Mental Theories (or Psychological Theories), (4) Instinct Theories, and (5) Combined Physical and Mental Theories. Nostalgia is a concept that describes sad and happy memories (Williams, 2004). Nostalgia is a preference (general desire, positive attitude, or effect) towards an object to remind a person of the past (Schindler, 1991). Everyone can feel nostalgia regardless of age, gender, social class, ethnicity, or another social group. Although initially rooted in psychology, nostalgia has also been developed through sociology and marketing to be more effective and persuasive (Larry, 1990). From a marketing point of view, nostalgia is present in various research contexts in terms of behavior, self-concept, brand loyalty, brand meaning, consumption preferences, and emotions (Muehling, n.d.). In general, nostalgia refers to the longing for the past in the short and long term or likes and activities that have been done in the past (Tan, 2020). Davis (1979) views nostalgia as memories, both positive and negative.

2.3 Attraction Traditional Values

In tourism activities, humans move from where they live and then travel to tourist destinations. This movement or displacement is only temporary because humans will return to their previous residence after the tourist activity is completed. Tourist destinations must have a particular attraction that makes tourists interested in visiting. This attraction can be of various kinds, ranging from attraction due to natural forms to the work of humans. So it can be said that attraction is one of the supporters of forming an area into a tourist destination. According to Zainuri (2018), a tourist attraction is something worthy of being offered to the tourist market due to its visual or experiential appeal. According to Suwanto (2004), a tourist attraction, also known as a tourist object, is a potential that attracts tourists to a tourist site. The items possessed by tourist sites play a significant role in luring travelers to visit and appreciate these items. According to the definition provided by experts, a tourist attraction is anything that encourages travelers to visit a tourist location to appreciate its uniqueness.

2.4 Brand Image

Brand image is the consumer's perception of a product's brand, shaped by the knowledge and experience gained through using the product. Moreover, brand image is a consumer's reaction to a brand based on the positive and negative aspects of the brand that customers recall. In the eyes of consumers, brand image is a belief about the product object that has been perceived (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012). Brand Image is a reflection of the brand's overall perception, which is shaped by information and past experiences. The brand's image is associated with attitudes in the form of beliefs and desires. Consumers with a favorable impression of a brand are more inclined to purchase (Nugroho J. Setiadi, 2013). Brand image is the favorable perception of the company's product brand in the minds of consumers. In choosing or evaluating the brand image of a product with a positive impression in their area, consumers evaluate brands based on product repute, product excellence, and ease of recognition.

2.5 Tourist Loyalty

In general, brand-loyal consumers will purchase the brand despite other competing brands offering more excellent product features when examined from various angles. If many brand consumers fall into this category when seen from various attribute perspectives, the brand has excellent brand equity. Brand equity is a collection of assets and liabilities associated with a brand, name, and symbol that can improve or decrease the value supplied by a product or service to both the firm and the customer (Durianto, 2013). The most loyal customers are the ones who purchase frequently and repeatedly. Customers who continue to make recurrent purchases are loyal. Customers regarded as loyal will subscribe to a service or make repeated purchases over a specified period. Loyal consumers are precious to businesses (Ali Hasan, 2013). Customer loyalty is exemplified by a customer's devotion to a brand, store, or supplier based on a highly positive attitude, as demonstrated by repeated purchases. Loyalty is both conduct and attitude. In other words, consumer loyalty can be determined by the brand of products/services they purchase and their feelings or attitudes toward the brand (F. Tjiptono, 2014).

The framework of this research can be described as follows.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a quantitative technique to investigate a specific population or sample. The population in this study is all unknown visitors; hence the sampling approach falls under the heading of non-probability sampling. The population in this study was visitors who had visited Lake Toba, and the sampling technique employed was accidental sampling, with the researchers selecting 320 tourists who had visited Lake Toba at least once. The data gathering technique then employs a questionnaire comprised of question items that characterize each indicator of the research variable. Finally, data were analyzed using AMOS-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

4. DISCUSSION

According to Amos' output, all indications for making the initial order buy choice have a substantial loading factor value greater than 0.5. If all of the construction indicators are statistically significant, they can be utilized to represent data analysis. The research model fitness test determines the research model's goodness of fit level. The GFI score assesses a model's ability to explain data variance. The GFI scale runs from 0 to 1. There are no standard standards for determining a good GFI score's upper and lower boundaries. However, it may be deduced that a good model is one with a GFI value close to 1. Many researchers, in practice, utilize a minimum limit of 0.9. Here are the findings of Amos' analysis:

Figure 2: Amos' Output Framework

Table 2: Results of Testing the Feasibility of Research Models for SEM Analysis

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut of Value	Analysis Results	Model Evaluation
Min fit function of chi-square	$p > 0.05$	($P = 0.951$)	Fit
Chi-square	Carmines & Mellow (1981) $df = 164 = 129.69$	3153.174	Fit
Non Centrality Parameter (NCP)	Cov-matrix deviation of sample and fitted < Chi-square	16687.382	Fit
Root Mean Square Error of Approx (RMSEA)	Browne and Cudeck (1993) < 0.08	0.499	Fit
A Model	AIC Model > Saturated AIC < Independence AIC	4372.174 > Saturated AIC (462.000) < Independence AIC (16939.382)	Fit
CAIC Model	CAIC Model < Saturated CAIC < Independence CAIC	4624.895 < Saturated CAIC (1563.482) > Independence CAIC (17039.517)	Not Fit
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	> 0.90	0.748	Not Fit
Parsimony Normed Fit Index (PNFI)	0.60 – 0.90	0.634	Fit
Parsimony Comparative Fit Index (PCFI)	0.60 – 0.90	0.64	Fit
PATIO	0.60 – 0.90	0.848	Fit
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	> 0.90 (Bentler (2000))	0.755	Fit
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	> 0.90 Byrne (1998)	0.955	Fit
Relative Fit Index (RFI)	0 – 1	0.702	Fit
The goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	> 0.90	0.94	Fit
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	> 0.90	0.903	Fit
Parsimony Goodness of Fit Index (PGFI)	0 – 1.0	0.416	Fit

Source: Amos' Output

Based on the Model Fit Assessment results, it is clear that all model analyses meet the standards for an SEM model. Path analysis was performed on each variable to determine the relationship between variables to see if there was a direct or indirect association. The results of the tests are shown in the table below.

a) Chi-Square

This test determines how well the projected covariance matrix matches the sample covariance matrix of the sample data. In practice, the P-value must be greater than or equal to 0.05 for the null hypothesis to be accepted, indicating that the model is valid. The Chi-square test is susceptible to sample size.

b) Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI)

GFI measures a model's capacity to account for data volatility. GFI values vary between 0 and 1. There are no standard criteria for an acceptable GFI score's boundaries. Nonetheless, it may be stated that a good model has a GFI value near 1. In practice, numerous researchers employ a minimum threshold of 0.90. GFI in SEM analysis is 0.910, which is between 0 and 1; this indicates that a model's ability to explain data variance is excellent/fit.

c) Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)

RMSEA measures the predicted population average difference per degree of freedom. RMSEA 0.08 indicates a good fit, while RMSEA 0.05 indicates a tight fit. The RMSEA result in this study is 0.268, indicating that the model is acceptable/fit.

d) Non-Centrality Parameter (NCP)

NCP is expressed as a re-specification of the Chi-square statistic. The evaluation is predicated on comparison to other models. The model is more effective as it lowers the NCP value. NCP is less than Chi-square, indicating that the model is valid.

e) Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index (AGFI)

AGFI is a version of the GFI that accommodates the model's degree of freedom (df) to the pdf of other models being compared. $AGFI > 0.9$ indicates an excellent fit, whereas $0.8 > AGFI > 0.9$ indicates a marginal fit. The AGFI value of 0.903% surpasses the number; hence the model is slightly acceptable.

f) Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)

TLI is often referred to as the non-normed fit index (NNFI). This is a measure for comparing models that consider the number of coefficients in the model. $TLI > 0.9$ indicates a decent fit, while $TLI > 0.9$ indicates a marginal fit. The TLI is between 0.8 and 0.9, or 0.911; therefore, the model is moderately fit.

g) Normed Fit Index (NFI)

The NFI value indicates the level of misalignment between the target model and the base model. NFI values vary between 0 and 1. $0.8 > NFI > 0.9$ implies a marginal fit, whereas $NFI > 0.9$ suggests a strong match. NFI is between 0.8 and 0.9, or 0.848; hence the model's fit is average.

h) Incremental Fit Index (IFI)

The IFI value is between 0 and 1. $IFI > 0.9$ indicates a decent fit, while $IFI > 0.9$ indicates a marginal fit. Comparative Fit Index (CFI) values vary from 0 to 1. $CFI > 0.9$ indicates a strong fit, but $CFI > 0.8$ indicates a marginal fit. The IFI score, 0.955, is greater than 0.9, so the model is moderately fit.

i) Relative Fit Index (RFI)

RFI values range from 0 and 1. $RFI > 0.9$ indicates an excellent fit, while $RFI > 0.9$ indicates a marginal fit. The RFI value is between 0 and 1, or 0.722; thus, the model is slightly appropriate.

j) Parsimonious Normed Fit Index (PNFI)

A high PNFI value signifies a more suitable match. PNFI is exclusively utilized to evaluate alternative models. The PNFI result is between 0.60 and 0.90, or 0.634, indicating that the model is moderately fit.

k) Parsimonious Goodness-Of-Fit Index (PGFI)

The PGFI value is a modified version of the GFI used to compare models, with a high number indicating a superior model. The PGFI value is between 0 and 0.90, which is 0.416, indicating that the model is suitable/fit.

l) Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)

The AIC value is utilized to compare models, with a smaller positive value indicating greater parsimony. Value of 4372.174 > Saturated AIC (462,000) Independence AIC (16939.382), hence making the model fit.

m) Consistent Akaike Information Criterion (CAIC)

This CAIC score is utilized for model comparisons, where a smaller positive number suggests greater parsimony. The model is fitted with a CAIC value of 4624.895 Saturated CAIC (1563.482) and Independence CAIC (17039.517).

Table 3: Standardized Direct Effects

	AT	NG	TF	BI	LW
BI	.227	-.133	.857	.000	.000
LW	.403	.271	.547	-.042	.000
LW4	.000	.000	.000	.000	.750
LW3	.000	.000	.000	.000	.767
LW2	.000	.000	.000	.000	.956
LW1	.000	.000	.000	.000	.936
BI3	.000	.000	.000	.801	.000
BI2	.000	.000	.000	.690	.000
BI1	.000	.000	.000	.673	.000
AT3	.521	.000	.000	.000	.000
AT2	.965	.000	.000	.000	.000
AT1	1.003	.000	.000	.000	.000
NG3	.000	.978	.000	.000	.000
NG2	.000	.966	.000	.000	.000
NG1	.000	.952	.000	.000	.000
TF5	.000	.000	.988	.000	.000
TF4	.000	.000	.998	.000	.000
TF3	.000	.000	.995	.000	.000
TF2	.000	.000	.979	.000	.000
TF1	.000	.000	.981	.000	.000

Source: Amos' Output (2022)

Table 4: Standardized Indirect Effects

	AT	NG	TF	BI	LW
BI	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
LW	.020	.018	.192	.000	.000
LW4	.217	.140	.381	-.034	.000
LW3	.212	.137	.373	-.034	.000
LW2	.317	.204	.556	-.050	.000
LW1	.302	.195	.531	-.048	.000
BI3	.187	-.102	.623	.000	.000
BI2	.140	-.076	.466	.000	.000
BI1	.138	-.075	.460	.000	.000
AT3	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
AT2	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
AT1	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
NG3	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
NG2	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
NG1	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
TF5	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
TF4	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
TF3	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
TF2	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
TF1	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Table 5: Standardized Total Effects

	AT	NG	TF	BI	LW
BI	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
LW	.029	.028	.311	.000	.000
LW4	.324	.224	.644	-.031	.000
LW3	.331	.229	.658	-.032	.000
LW2	.413	.286	.821	-.040	.000
BI3	.182	-.106	.687	.000	.000
BI2	.157	-.092	.592	.000	.000
BI1	.153	-.089	.577	.000	.000
AT3	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
AT2	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
AT1	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
NG3	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
NG2	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
NG1	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
TF5	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
TF4	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
TF3	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
TF2	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
TF1	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Table 6: Estimation results of CR (Critical Ratio) and P-Value

			Estimate	SE.	CR.	P	Label
BI	<---	TF	.460	.034	13.384	***	par_16
BI	<---	NG	-.075	.023	-3.316	***	par_17
BI	<---	AT	.138	.025	5.544	***	par_18
LW	<---	TF	.338	.040	8.472	***	par_22
LW	<---	NG	.176	.009	20.234	***	par_23
LW	<---	AT	.282	.011	24.716	***	par_24
LW	<---	KW	.249	.039	6.376	***	par_25
LW	<---	BI	-.048	.042	-1.152	.249	par_26
TF1	<---	TF	1.000				
TF2	<---	TF	.999	.016	62.047	***	par_1
TF3	<---	TF	1.022	.013	80.611	***	par_2
TF4	<---	TF	1.023	.012	86.259	***	par_3
TF5	<---	TF	.998	.014	70.019	***	par_4
NG1	<---	NG	1.000				
NG2	<---	NG	1.020	.024	41.946	***	par_5
NG3	<---	NG	1.003	.022	45.269	***	par_6
AT1	<---	AT	1.000				
AT2	<---	AT	.981	.015	63.359	***	par_7
AT3	<---	AT	.621	.057	10.919	***	par_8
BI1	<---	BI	1.000				
BI2	<---	BI	1.012	.093	10.882	***	par_9
BI3	<---	BI	1.354	.110	12.319	***	par_10
LW1	<---	LW	1.000				
LW2	<---	LW	1.048	.028	37.175	***	par_13
LW3	<---	LW	.703	.036	19.688	***	par_14
LW4	<---	LW	.718	.038	18.879	***	par_15

Source: Attachment to Amos (2022)

Effect of Tourist Facilities on Brand Image

Data study reveals that the quality of Lake Toba's tourist infrastructure directly and substantially impacts the lake's reputation. This study's findings corroborate those of another titled, "The Role of Tourist Destination Development in Building its Brand Image: A Conceptual Model" by Manrai (2016). Both found that visitors' perceptions of a destination's quality improved when tourist amenities were present. Furthermore, Lusch, R. F., & Vargo, S. L. (2006) illustrate that innovative services can give a positive impression to a tourist. Innovative services will continue to be perfected following the expectations of tourists. The implication of the findings in the study shows that so far, the brand image of Lake Toba is known as an unmaintained lake and has not shown an extraordinary increase in the provision of tourist facilities. Tourist facilities such as existing hotels have not increased from year to year.

Effect of Nostalgia on Brand Image

The data analysis shows that nostalgia directly and substantially impacts Lake Toba's brand image. Findings from this study are consistent with those from a study by Altuna (2019) titled *The Role of Nostalgia Proneness in the Effect of Brand Image, Corporate Image, Brand Trust, and Consumer Involvement on Emotional Attachment: Global vs. Local Brand*, which found that nostalgia has a significant impact on the brand image of travel destinations. Huan (2014) stated that a tourist's good memories after visiting a destination could motivate him to remember the event in the future. Furthermore, Heo (2018) suggests that nostalgia is an essential element for a tourist in deciding which tourist destination to use as a vacation reference, which is done personally, with family, or in groups of colleagues in the company.

Effect of Attraction on Brand Image

It emerges from the research that attraction directly and substantially impacts brand perception. Consistent with Lee's (2021) prior research titled *The Effect of Confirmation of Nation Brand Image in International Tourism Advertisement on Travel Intention of Foreign Tourists: The Case of Korean ITA for Chinese Tourists*, our findings highlight the significance of allure when it comes to establishing a positive brand image among consumers. Furthermore, Damanik (2022) explains that the emotional response of a tourist can be shown through the natural and cultural beauty that exists in a tourist destination. The findings in this study imply that the central government has designated Lake Toba as one of the mainstay priorities in encouraging local and foreign tourist visits. The attraction started in 2018 is the implementation of an international marathon event where 8 countries participated in this activity. However, this attraction activity is still considered less effective in increasing the interest of tourist visits. Furthermore, in 2019, an international marathon event was held where participants who participated in this activity were livelier than the previous year.

Effect of Tourist Facilities on Tourist Loyalty

Data study seems to indicate that tourist amenities directly and considerably impact visitor loyalty. These findings are consistent with those of a study titled *Loyalty on Ecotourism* analyzed using the factors of tourist attraction, safety, and amenities, with satisfaction as an intervening variable (Nugroho, 2019), which found that such amenities significantly influenced visitors' willingness to return. Furthermore, Toffolo (2021) states that tourist facilities through sustainable ecotourism are a choice in adding the attributes of tourist facilities. Next, Purwasih (2020) makes it clear that supporting facilities are needed to support tourists' loyalty through the provision of religious facilities and or halal restaurants.

Effect of Nostalgia on Tourist Loyalty

The results of data analysis show that nostalgia has a significant effect on tourist loyalty in Lake Toba. The results of this study are in line with the results of Christou's study (2020) entitled *Tourism experiences as the remedy to nostalgia: conceptualizing the nostalgia and tourism nexus*, which indicates that nostalgia has a significant effect on tourist loyalty. Furthermore, Tan (2020) reinforces that when tourists feel expectations with reality are

appropriate, this will impact the formation of experiences, where the experience can direct tourists to remain loyal to visiting destination destinations in the future.

Effect of Attraction on Tourist Loyalty

Data analysis reveals that visits to a particular attraction positively impact repeat business from vacationers. This study's findings corroborate those of a prior one by Diah Yulisetiari (2018) titled *The Contribution of Tourist Attraction, Accessibility, and Amenities in Creating Tourist Loyalty in Indonesia*, which found that visitors' perceptions of a destination's attractiveness had a substantial impact on their likelihood to return. Furthermore, Hussein (2020) also confirmed that festival activities carried out sustainably will be able to attract tourists to choose tourist destinations. Then Brien (2021) explained that the support from the government in the activities of attractions in tourist destinations could give tourists confidence that what they have chosen is correct and does provide added value.

Effect of Brand Image on Tourist Loyalty

Data investigation revealed that consumers' brand perception did not influence their loyalty. Relationships between Service Quality, Brand Image, Customer Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty by Cuong (2021) finds that brand image significantly affects customer loyalty, which contradicts the current study's findings. These findings are consistent with those of Suryawan's (2020) study, *The Influence of Brand Awareness, Brand Image, and Brand Trust on Brand Loyalty*, which found that brand image did not significantly affect customer loyalty. Then Angga (2019) stated that managing the brand image well will foster a high sense of trust in customers. One of the efforts must be made is that, as much as possible, the company responds quickly and appropriately to customer complaints.

Effect of Tourist Facilities on Tourist Loyalty through Brand Image

Analysis of the data shows that the relationship between tourist amenities and customer loyalty is mediated, in part, by the perception of the brand. This study's findings are consistent with those of another study (Anastassova, 2015) titled *Tourist loyalty and destination brand image perception: The case of Sunny Guests' impressions of a destination's brand is crucial to their overall satisfaction and repeat visits*, according to a study conducted on the Sunny Beach Resort in Bulgaria. Furthermore, Weia (2020) states that brand image is the belief of tourists in their perception of tourist destinations. When these tourist facilities are considered feasible and complete, tourists primarily prefer the tourist destination they choose.

Effect of Nostalgia on Tourists' Loyalty through Brand Image

Data study suggests that brand image is a mediator between nostalgia's influence on tourist loyalty and the target market. Findings from this study are consistent with those from *A bite of nostalgia: The role of nostalgia in consumers' loyalty intentions in traditional restaurants* by Zhang (2020), which found that nostalgic feelings can motivate visitors to become loyal to a business. The existence of good memories causes tourists to assess the brand image of the tourist object destined to be more positive. Furthermore, Chen (2020) emphasized that giving

a first impression to new tourists is the first step in providing the most beautiful memories as an effort to present a positive image.

Effect of Attraction on Tourists' Loyalty through Brand Image

Data study reveals the importance of brand image in balancing out the influence of attractions on visitors' allegiances. Similarly, Hussein's (2020) Predicting Tourist Loyalty toward Cultural Creative Attractions the Moderating Role of Demographic Factors finds that the results of this study are consistent with his findings, which indicate that attraction can influence tourist loyalty through demographic factors. Furthermore, Radha (2020) explains that the existence of attraction activities can attract tourists. This is indeed inseparable from the brand image attached to tourist destinations.

5. CONCLUSION

Researchers can conclude that all variables, namely tour facilities, nostalgia, and appeal, directly and significantly impact Lake Toba's brand image and tourist loyalty. However, brand image has a negligible impact on tourist loyalty. The brand image then indirectly plays an essential role in mediating the impacts of tour facilities, nostalgia, and appeal on Lake Toba tourists' loyalty. The recommendation that the researcher proposes is that synchronized work is needed from various parties to improve the image of Lake Toba to the broader community. Travel bureaus, airlines, and related agencies such as the education office of North Sumatra Province should schedule every public and private school to make a minimum of cultural tourism visits. Thus, the concept of educational and historical values, especially in North Sumatra, can be known by the younger generation.

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